

A REVIEW ON PANCHAMRUT AS A MATERNAL NUTRITIONAL SUPPORT IN GARBHINI PARICHARYA

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ABSTRACT

Background: Pregnancy is a critical phase requiring adequate maternal nutrition for optimal fetal growth and maternal health. Ayurveda describes specific dietary guidelines under **Garbhini Paricharya**, emphasizing *Madhura, Sheeta & Drava Ahar* for antenatal care. **Panchamrut**, a traditional formulation consisting of milk, curd, ghee, honey, and sugar, is considered a nourishing and rejuvenating preparation. **Objective:** To review **Panchamrut** as a nutritional supplement for maternal–fetal wellbeing during pregnancy based on classical Ayurvedic literature and modern nutritional perspectives. **Methods:** A narrative review of Ayurvedic classical texts, including *Charaka Samhita, Sushruta Samhita, and Ashtanga Hridaya*, along with relevant contemporary research, was conducted. **Results:** **Panchamrut** fulfills the criteria of *Madhura, Sheeta,*

and *Drava Ahar* and provides significant portion of the **macronutrients** (carbohydrates, proteins, fats) and **micronutrients** (calcium, vitamins, and minerals) required during pregnancy. It exhibits *Rasayana, Balya, and Medhya* properties, supporting maternal strength, digestion, immunity, and fetal development. **Conclusion:** **Panchamrut** is a simple, cost-effective, and holistic Ayurvedic nutritional supplement that supports maternal–fetal wellbeing during pregnancy.

KEYWORDS: Panchamrut, Maternal–Fetal Wellbeing, Nutritional Supplement, Madhura, Sheeta, Drava Ahar, Garbhini Paricharya.

INTRODUCTION

Pregnancy is a physiologically and emotionally significant phase in a woman's life, requiring enhanced nutritional and metabolic demands. In Ayurveda, this stage is comprehensively managed under **Garbhini Paricharya**, which emphasizes diet, lifestyle, and mental wellbeing for healthy fetal development.

Fetal development is entirely dependent on maternal nutrition, highlighting the importance of proper dietary intake. *Sushruta Samhita* also emphasizes balanced nutrition and healthy lifestyle practices during pregnancy for optimal outcomes.

Among the recommended dietary components, *Madhura* (sweet), *Sheeta* (cooling), and *Drava* (liquid) foods are considered ideal. **Panchamrut**, a combination of five nourishing ingredients, aligns with these principles and is traditionally used to enhance maternal and fetal health.

In line with this, the *Sushruta Sutra* (14.12) states:

"रसजं पुरुषं विद्यात् रसम् रक्षेत् प्रयत्नतः।
अन्नपानाच्च मतिमान् आचाराचप्यतन्द्रितः॥"

"The individual (purusha) is born or nourished by the ahaar rasa. For this, the ahaar rasa must be carefully preserved to avoid its corruption. One should always exercise vigilance, ensuring that no distortion occurs in the ahaar rasa, and thereby in the intake of food, drink, and actions. Only then will the ahaar rasa remain intact, maintaining the nourishment and vitality of the body." This verse underscores the Ayurvedic principle that mindful eating and an understanding of the nourishing ahara rasa play an essential role in supporting both maternal and fetal wellbeing during pregnancy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study is a narrative literature review based on classical Ayurvedic texts including *Charaka Samhita*, *Sushruta Samhita*, and *Ashtanga Hridaya*, along with published research articles from Ayurvedic journals and databases such as PubMed and AYUSH literature repositories.

Conceptual Review of Panchamrut:

Panchamrut is derived from Sanskrit words “Panch” (five) and “Amrut” (nectar), meaning a divine combination of five life-sustaining ingredients:

- **Cow milk** (*Ksheera*)
- **Curd** (*Dadhi*)
- **Ghee** (*Go-Ghrita*)
- **Honey** (*Madhu*)
- **Sugar** (*Sharkara*)

Cows Milk – Milk is *saatmya*, *jeevaniya dravya* (a life-enhancing compound) for all. So, it is one of *pathya dravya*. According to Acharya Charaka milk is described as *swadhu* (sweet), *sheeta* (cold), *mridhu* (soft), *snigdha* (oily), *bahala* (thick), *slakshna* (smooth), *pichchila* (slimy), *guru* (heavy), *manda* (slow), *prasanna* (clear). It is said to enhance *oja* (life force) and *jeevanashakti* and is considered superior to other types of milk and the most effective rejuvenating tonic (*rasayana*).

Ghee – It is *madhur*, *sheeta*, *Snigdha* (unctuousness), *Sheeta* (cold), *Guru* (heavy), *Mridu* (soft), *Sowmya* (soft by nature), *Sūkshma* (minute), *Anabhishtyandi* (which does not cause obstruction of channels), *Alpābhishtyandi* (which mildly may cause obstruction of channels). *Goghrita* (cow ghee) acts as *Rasa Vardhaka* (increases *Rasa*) and also increases other components of the body such as, *Shukra* (semen), *Ojas* (essence of all *Dhatus*).

Honey – It has *Yogavahi* property, which means that it accelerates the properties of the substance it is combined with, without undergoing a change in its own properties.

Curd – *Rochan* ((Improves taste/Appetizer), *Deepana* (increases digestive fire), *Vrushya* (increases semen), *Balvardhak* (increases strength), *Brihan*, *Mangalyam*, *Sneham* when properly consumed.

Sugar – *Madhura Rasa*, nourishing and cooling in nature

These ingredients synergistically enhance each other's properties when combined.

Panchamrut as *Madhura*, *Sheeta* and *Drava Ahar* in Pregnancy:

Ayurveda recommends *Madhura Rasa*, *Sheeta Virya*, and *Drava Ahar* during pregnancy to support fetal nourishment and maternal stability.

Panchamrut fulfills these dietary requirements

- **Madhura (Sweet):** Promotes tissue growth and nourishment
- **Sheeta (Cooling):** Maintains physiological balance
- **Drava (Liquid):** Enhances digestibility and absorption

Overall it enhances quality of **Rasa dhatu**, which directly nourishes fetus via placenta and ensures continuous nutrient flow (like modern placental transfer) which Prevents fetal hypoxia and growth retardation. Madhura–Sheeta–Snigdha Aahara prescribed in Ayurveda plays a fundamental role in maintaining **dosha equilibrium, dhatu nourishment, and mala regulation**, thereby optimizing **placental function and fetal growth** while preventing Garbha Vyapadā such as Upaviṣṭaka. This demonstrates a comprehensive integrative understanding of maternal nutrition and fetal development in classical Ayurvedic literature.

Modern Nutritional Values of Panchamrut and Its Use in Pregnancy:

In modern nutritional terms, **Panchamrut** is a highly nutritious and energy-dense combination. Each ingredient provides vital macronutrients and micronutrients essential for both maternal and fetal health:

- **Milk:** A rich source of **calcium, protein, and vitamin D**, which supports fetal bone development, tissue growth, and immunity. Calcium is essential during pregnancy to support the development of the fetal skeleton and to prevent maternal bone loss.
- **Curd:** Packed with **probiotics, protein, and calcium**, which help in maintaining gut health and enhancing digestion, along with improving immunity.
- **Ghee:** A source of **healthy fats and fat-soluble vitamins** such as **vitamin A, D, and E**, which are essential for fetal brain development and maintaining maternal energy levels.
- **Honey:** Provides natural **sugars** such as **glucose and fructose**, serving as a quick source of energy. It also has antimicrobial properties that support overall health.
- **Sugar:** **Carbohydrates** in the form of **sucrose** provide essential energy for the mother and fetus, especially in the second and third trimesters when fetal growth accelerates.

Modern Research supports the efficacy of these ingredients for boosting maternal energy, enhancing fetal growth, and maintaining the mother's health during pregnancy. A balanced intake of these nutrients helps in reducing the risk of pregnancy-related complications like **gestational diabetes, preeclampsia, and anemia**.

Role in Maternal–Fetal Wellbeing:

Maternal Benefits

- Enhances strength (*Balya*)
- Improves digestion (*Agni deepana*)
- Boosts immunity (*Vyadhikshamatva*)
- Supports mental stability (*Medhya effect*)
- Supports ease of labor and delivery: Following the principles of Garbhini Paricharya promotes proper alignment of the body's vital organs, such as the *udar* (abdomen), *kukshi* (uterus), *kati* (lower back), *parshwa* (sides), and *prushtha* (back). This results in a smoother and more comfortable pregnancy and delivery. Additionally, the practice of mindful eating and proper dietary choices ensures that **vayu** (wind) is in balance, facilitating natural processes like urination and defecation, maintaining smooth skin, and preventing complications during labor.

Fetal Benefits

- Promotes growth and development (*Garbha poshana*)
- Enhances cognitive development (*Medhya property*)
- Supports healthy fetal weight
- Ensures balanced development through a nourishing and well-maintained maternal environment.

DISCUSSION

The principles of **Garbhini Paricharya** strongly emphasize the use of *Madhura*, *Snigdha*, and *Drava Ahar* for ensuring proper fetal nourishment and maternal health. **Panchamrut**, being a combination of five classical nourishing substances, aligns well with these principles. Classical texts such as *Charaka Samhita*, *Sushruta Samhita*, and *Ashtanga Hridaya* highlight the importance of each ingredient individually for strength, immunity, and rejuvenation. Their combined use in **Panchamrut** provides synergistic nutritional and therapeutic benefits. Modern nutritional science also supports the inclusion of dairy-based products and natural sweeteners during pregnancy for energy, calcium supply, and metabolic support, thereby validating Ayurvedic concepts.

Furthermore, as emphasized in the *Sushruta Sutra* (14.12), the essence of food (*rasam*) is best preserved when one is mindful of their eating habits. Engaging in careful and deliberate consumption of food, particularly during pregnancy, can ensure that both the mother and the

fetus benefit from optimal nutrition and nourishment. The main intension of advising *Garbhini Paricharya* is *Paripurnatya* (providing growth of mother and fetus), *Anupaghata* (pregnancy without complications), *Sukhaprasava* (for healthy delivery and healthy child) is fulfilled by consumption of panchamrut.

CONCLUSION

Panchamrut is a classical Ayurvedic formulation that serves as an effective nutritional supplement during pregnancy. It aligns with the principles of **Garbhini Paricharya** and fulfills the requirements of *Madhura, Sheeta and Drava Ahar*. Its balanced composition provides essential nutrients, enhances maternal strength, supports fetal development, and improves overall wellbeing. Thus, **Panchamrut** represents a simple, safe, and holistic approach to antenatal nutrition rooted in classical Ayurvedic wisdom.

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